

TARGETED AND EFFECTIVE USE OF INVESTMENT IN
CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

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In this article, a wide range of construction and investment projects implemented in our country and methods of increasing their effectiveness are discussed.

Key words: *investment, investment project, construction, Capital, Commercial Bank, interest rate, project.*

Introduction. The further development of the construction sector on a global scale, the formation of institutional units in the construction sector and the introduction of digital technologies into the industry are leading to an increase in the number of exteriors for effective investment projects. The construction sector does not develop at the level of modern talabi without the provision of adequate innovations. The development of the construction sector at the level of modern requirements, the direct supplier of innovative development of favorable conditions for life and entrepreneurship are effective investment projects. Research is being conducted on the activity of investment projects in the world economy, their new forms of innovation and the widespread use of elements of the digital economy. Investment projects, in turn, create a new technical, technological, information, social, economic, organizational system or change existing systems and reduce the consumption of resources to the account of products, improve the quality of Service and achieve high economic efficiency. The absence of normative bases and indications for determining the effectiveness of investment projects, the independent approach of each sphere to determining and increasing the effectiveness of investment projects, the effective use of advanced experience in this direction are relevant in the conditions of market economy.

Analysis of thematic literature. Great attention is paid to the issues of research on the use of investment in the construction sector and their effectiveness in the scientific work of foreign scientists. In particular, William F. from foreign authors Sharp, P.Shtolte, Richard A. Brealey, L.Gitman, M.Djang [1]. Within the framework of the research, the work of these scientists was studied from a comprehensive and critical point of view.

The following scientists conducted a systematic study on the problems of attracting investment resources from scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States and increasing their effectiveness: A. Abramov, Lishinsky A. S., A. Goncharov, Lobkin S. M., Rezer V. S., Blank I. A., Rimer M. I., T. Blokhina, Kovalev V. V and others [2]. In the research carried out by these scientists, the issues of investment are devoted to one or

more areas of the general economy, and increasing the effectiveness of investment projects in the construction sector is not particularly emphasized.

In our country, in the years of independence, literature, scientific articles, educational and methodological manuals devoted to the effectiveness of investment projects and their problems are published. These are the words A. V. Vakhobov, Sh. X. Khajibakiev, N. G. Muminov, Sh. I. Mustafakulav, B. I. Komiljonov, M. A. Raimjonova, G. A. Samatov, B. B. It is possible to add the research of the valievs [3,4]. The research of these authors has an important scientific and practical significance and has made a great contribution to the development of modern methods and methods of increasing the efficiency of investment projects in our country.

Analysis and results. The issue of increasing the efficiency of investment and construction activities is considered an urgent task, determined mainly by determining the cost of capital construction at the regional and corporate levels of management and improving the planning system. With the transition of the domestic economy to market relations, the role of SMEs in assessing the costs of investment projects has increased significantly. Advanced International experience shows that the success of investment projects and activities of investment companies is largely determined by the quality of design and estimate documents and the development of long-term and current capital construction plans [4]. As a result of the improvement of project documentation and production technology, the reduction of construction costs plays a significant role in increasing investment efficiency and ultimately serves to improve capital investments and the technological structure of the main capital.

Investments play an important role in supporting and increasing the country's economic potential, modernizing and diversifying economic sectors, activating economic growth, increasing the competitiveness of products and services in domestic and foreign markets. Investments will lead to the growth of GDP, the development of enterprises and the country's export potential.

To solve the issue of attracting investments in the economy of the territory, it is necessary to develop a territorial investment policy. And the regional investment policy is the activity of the Territorial Administration bodies, which should seek the source of investment and focus on the areas in which they are effectively used. The purpose of the investment policy can be explained by the following:

1. Implementation of structural changes, development of priority networks.
2. Support small business and private entrepreneurship.
3. Create additional jobs.
4. Attracting investment resources from all sources.
5. Non-profit investment funds, at the same time the establishment of venture funds.
6. Expanding the use of leasing in innovation activities.
7. Improvement of the system of preferences.
8. Provide an investment environment and attractiveness.

The analysis of these directions is considered one of the current issues.

Achieving balanced regional socio-economic growth is important in ensuring macroeconomic stability and balanced economic growth rates in the strategic context of

our republic. The existence of asymmetric discrepancies in the current regional socio-economic development, the efficient use of the available economic resource potential and the implementation of an active territorial investment policy aimed at revitalizing economic development in a relatively low-developed region are necessary. On the basis of proper assessment and management of the regional financial and investment potential, it seeks to deepen the reforms to further revive investment activity.

In 2017-2021 in the strategy of actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the near future, the implementation of tasks "improvement of investment climate, active involvement of foreign, first of all, direct foreign investments in the sectors and regions of the country's economy" has been defined.

Table 1.

The main capital in uzbekistanalga investments and their distribution by Regions (billion. sum)

Regions name	Years						Growth in 2015 year compared to 2020 year, in percentage
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	
Total by Republic	28694,6	35233,3	41670,5	49770,6	60719,2	107333,0	374,1
Republic Of Karakalpakstan	2361,9	3917,8	5925,7	3718,9	2235	6046,4	256,0
Andijan region	1287,8	1423	1661	1987,3	2236	4056,0	315,0
Bukhara region	2871,6	3408,3	3866,1	5756,7	11008,9	7846,1	273,2
Jizzakh region	1017,9	1038,5	1101,1	1247	1436,7	3169,2	311,3
Kashkadarya region	3498,8	4483,2	5590,5	7048,8	10181,9	15321,1	437,9
Navoi region	1622,6	1653	1685,4	2846,8	2784,5	10059,1	619,9
Namangan region	1059,3	1618,7	1966,4	2566,7	3052	7131,0	673,2
Samarkand region	1915	2247,8	2854	3321,4	3307,1	5746,9	300,1
Surkhandarya region	1246,8	1339,5	1633,4	2005,2	2949,1	6111,0	490,1
Sirdarya region	804,7	927,2	1000,2	1240,9	1349,4	2154,6	267,8
Tashkent region	2982,9	3741,9	4055,7	3959,9	4301,8	9351,4	313,5
Fergana region	1899,7	1998,4	2133	2404,5	2473,8	4978,4	262,1
Khorezm region	1148,5	1466,5	1343,4	1445,4	1877,1	2980,0	259,5
Tashkent City	4977,1	5969,5	6854,6	10221,1	11525,9	21861,5	439,2

In 2021, our country is planning to invest about 138 trillion soums or 16 percent more than in 2020 from the account of all sources. In this regard, the amount of foreign direct investment is increased by 1.5 times compared to the current year, reaching 4.2 billion dollars, as a result of which 142 modern enterprises are planned to be launched.

Consistent implementation of the regional economic policy on these tasks constitutes the fundamental basis for determining the strategic directions of the regional investment policy in the future.

As can be seen from Table 1 data, the main capital by the Republic algebra investments amounted to 28694,6 billion in nominal terms. sum, which has a consistent growth rate of 107 333.0 billion by 2018. who asked. So, in these years, the growth in the nominal content of investments in which the main capital algebra was invested was 3,7 times.

The main capital investments in Uzbekistan accounted for 374.1 per cent of the growth in 2020 compared to 2015. High growth rates are observed in Kashkadarya (437,9 percent), Namangan (673,2 percent), Navoi (619,9 percent), Surkhandarya (49,1 percent) regions and Tashkent (439,2 percent).

The role and importance of the main capital investments in the socio-economic development of the regions can be explained by the following:

first, the growth of the scale of investment in fixed capital algebra as a factor of high technological progress and intensive economic growth will positively affect the annual growth rate of the GDP;

secondly, the diversification of the economy, the implementation of structural reforms will ultimately make it possible to establish the production of import substitutes and export-oriented products;

therefore, in the context of rational use of the existing financial and investment potential, it ensures the broad development of entrepreneurial activity and, ultimately, the improvement of the welfare of the population through the creation of new jobs. As a result, the increase in the gross demand in the economy on account of the consistent increase in the income of the population creates conditions for the further development of production.

It will be possible to determine the investment activity of each territory by means of the average indicator of the nominal amount of investments included in the main capital algebra in the cross-section of the regions by the total Republic.

2-table.

The share of regions in fixed capital investments in Uzbekistan, (in percentage terms of total)

Name of the regions	Main capital algebra the share of regions in investments, in percentage					
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Total by Republic	100	100	100	100	100	100
Republic Of Karakalpakstan	8,23	11,12	14,22	7,47	3,68	5,6
Andijan region	4,49	4,04	3,99	3,99	3,68	3,8
Bukhara region	10,01	9,67	9,28	11,57	18,13	7,3
Jizzakh region	3,55	2,95	2,64	2,51	2,37	3,0
Kashkadarya region	12,19	12,72	13,42	14,16	16,77	14,3
Navoi region	5,65	4,69	4,04	5,72	4,59	9,4
Namangan region	3,69	4,59	4,72	5,16	5,03	6,6
Samarkand region	6,67	6,38	6,85	6,67	5,45	5,4
Surkhandarya region	4,35	3,80	3,92	4,03	4,86	5,7
Sirdarya region	2,80	2,63	2,40	2,49	2,22	2,0
Tashkent region	10,40	10,62	9,73	7,96	7,08	8,7
Fergana region	6,62	5,67	5,12	4,83	4,07	4,6

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Khorezm region	4,00	4,16	3,22	2,90	3,09	2,8
Tashkent City	17,35	16,94	16,45	20,54	18,98	20,4

According to Table 2, the highest figure in investments with the main capital in the Republic corresponds to the city of Tashkent. In particular, the share of the city of Tashkent in investments with a total capital of 17.35% was accounted for in 2015, although in 2016 and 2017 there was a decrease compared to 18.98% by 2018 and 20.4% by 2019. During the period of analysis on this indicator, high growth was observed in Kashkadarya region (14.3 percent), Tashkent region (8.7 percent), and in 2020 it is divided into leading indicators (Table 2). However, in the regions of Sirdarya (2 per cent), Khorezm (2.8 per cent) and Jizzakh (3,0 per cent), this figure remains relatively low in the Republic. In the conditions of the current reforms, the issue of increasing investment activity through the rational use of available financial and investment potential in each of the regions is emerging as a topical issue on the agenda.

These data need to be evaluated positively, because investing in expansion, reconstruction and modernization is the most effective direction that will allow to ensure the effectiveness of the investment process in the shortest possible time and at minimum cost. These data are also indirect evidence of the innovative development of the economy. It is of great practical interest to evaluate the optimization of the reproductive structure, the harmony of proportions, and, of course, with the acceleration of innovative processes, the ratio will change in favor of investments aimed at modernization, technical and technological re-equipment.

Investment in construction the launch of projects is a complex process, especially when it comes to investments that have received a lot of financial and time resources. Before making a decision to start such investments, the investor should familiarize himself with a number of important technical and economic assumptions related to various expert opinions and analyzes, including planned investments.

The main ones are as follows: [5]

- investment projects goals;
- planned costs required for investment projects;
- volume and composition of investment projects;
- criteria and methods used in assessing the effectiveness of investment projects;
- program for working on the project
- its implementation, execution deadlines.

Given the above assumptions, the investor should choose to abandon the project and accept it. The problem is usually the level of management and involves choosing the most effective project and this is the greatest opportunity or best to achieve success. The whole thing will depend on the decision-making. Investing in bonds, as well as any financial instruments or development and innovation projects, leads to the fact that the investor makes a decision under certain risk conditions.

Conclusion. The effectiveness of investment projects in construction can lead to different results in the future, which can be attributed to different factors. Some factors can not be determined in any way, so it is impossible to include them in the digital analysis. Despite the many dimensions that exist at the modern statistical level, it is difficult to

measure and analyze, for example, the political situation or, to a lesser extent, the economic situation in the world. The main question that comes to mind in this regard is how to make predictions based on different profit rates in order to approach the highest possible level of status in the future[6]. Determining the norm of earnings from investments in construction, investment serves as the basis for making decisions.

Today, the criteria used in the evaluation of projects and the analysis of investment activities in the context of their decision-making and which of them is used in the formation of the capital investment budget can be divided into two groups, depending on whether the time parameters are taken into account or not:

- a) based on discounted price;
- b) based on account ratings.

The first group includes the following criteria:

- Net Present Value – (NPU);
- Profitability Index – (PI);
- Internal Rate of Return – (IRR);
- Modified Internal Rate of Return – (MIRR);
- Discounted Payback Period – (DPP).

The second group includes the following criteria:

- Payback Period – (PP);
- Accounting Rate of Return – (ARR).

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